

incidence in Oct, when temperatures were 20.7-32.7 °C with a mean rainfall of 18.2 mm. In general, thrips damage was high after heavy rains followed by a prolonged (40-45 d) dry spell. □

***Heliothis armigera* development and damage to rice**

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Heliothis armigera (Hübner), a highly polyphagous insect, has occasionally been reported as a rice pest. Larvae from six host plants — maize, sorghum, wheat, pigeonpea, mungbean, and tobacco — were reared on the hosts. Upon emergence, mated pairs from each host were caged in 12- × 39-cm mylar tubes with 30- and 75-d-old IR1917-3-17 rice plants. Honey solution (10%) was added in a wick receptacle.

Moths laid eggs on the rice leaves and fully exerted panicles for 5 d. Growth and development of *H. armigera* and potential damage of rice panicles by larvae were determined.

The six phenotypes of *Heliothis* laid more eggs on 75-d-old plants, with 88% of the eggs laid on grains between the lemma and palea (see table). The higher

Development and gain damage by 6 *Heliothis armigera* phenotypes^a on IR1917-3-17 rice.^b IRRI greenhouse, Nov 1985-May 1986.

Phenotype source	Ovipositional preference ^c		Egg hatch (%)	Larval wt (mg)	Growth index ^d	Adult		Damaged grains ^e (%)
	(no. of eggs/plant)					Wt (mg)	Longevity (d)	
	30 DAS	75 DAS						
Pigeonpea	6 c	62 c	87 a	88 c	-	-	-	31 b
Mungbean	8 c	88 b	90 a	81 c	-	-	-	28 b
Tobacco	6 c	59 c	88 a	79 c	-	-	-	20 c
Maize	26 a	110 a	94 a	126 a	0.3 ab	157 a	4 a	45 a
Sorghum	18 b	94 ab	86 a	119 a	0.2 b	143 b	4 a	40 a
Wheat	22 ab	103 a	92 a	102 b	0.4 a	138 b	2 b	19 c

^a *Heliothis* phenotype from tobacco was collected by Dr. K. Klaus from Pangasinan. ^b In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^c DAS = days after sowing. ^d Growth index = no. of larvae becoming pupae (%) divided by mean developmental period (d). ^e Damaged grains = no. of grains with holes/450 grains × 100 (Note: the number of grains of 5 panicles was thinned to 450).

oviposition rate in 75-d-old rice plants could have been triggered by their floral nectar production.

Egg hatch was high, 86-94%. Newly hatched larvae readily fed on young leaves and soon dispersed. Larvae that were able to locate the panicles grew; those that failed, died.

Heliothis phenotypes from legumes and tobacco developed only to the 4th instar. Phenotypes reared from graminaceous crops — maize, sorghum, and wheat — developed completely.

Rice and these crops may have similar

chemical constituents.

Development from egg to adult took 39-52 d. No additional molt (7th instar) that prolonged larval development was observed.

Host potential of rice was very low, with a 0.2-0.4 growth index, 79-126 mg larvae weight, 138-152 mg adult weight, and 24 d adult longevity.

The larval stages of all phenotypes damaged grain. In a no-choice test, larvae produced 19-45% damaged grains. The damage was similar to that made by *Conocephalus*. □

Pest Control and Management WEEDS

Evaluation of weed control methods in Bhutan

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Labor constraints can make timely weeding of rice crops difficult in Bhutan. We compared hand and rotary weeding with butachlor alone or supplemented with a single hand or rotary weeding. The trial was conducted at CARD in a split-plot design with three replications. Varieties Pusa 33 and IR36 were subplot

Effect of weed control method on rice yield. CARD, Wangdiphodrang, Bhutan, 1984.

Weed control method	Mean grain yield ^a (t/ha, 14% MC)			Weeding operation		RAVC ^e MBCR ^e (\$) (negative)
	Pusa 33	IR36	Mean ^b	Time ^c (d/ha)	Cost ^d (\$/ha)	
	Rotary weeding 35 DT	5.9	6.0	5.9 bcd	16	
Rotary weeding 21 and 40 DT	5.6	5.9	5.8 cd	22	18	1196
Hand weeding 35 DT	5.2	5.6	5.4 d	27	22	1102
Hand weeding 21 and 40 DT	5.4	6.0	5.7 cd	53	44	1153
Butachlor 2 DT	6.3	1.2	6.8 abc	2	50	1368
Butachlor 2 DT + rotary weeding 35 DT	5.8	6.8	6.3 abcd	7	55	1270
Butachlor 2 DT + hand weeding 35 DT	6.5	6.6	6.5 ab	9	56	1317
Weedy check	4.2	4.8	4.5 e	-	-	-
Weed-free check	6.7	7.1	6.9 a	-	-	-

^a MC = moisture content. ^b Separation of means by DMRT at the 5% level. ^c Includes time taken to apply butachlor. ^d Based on a labor cost of \$0.83/day. Includes cost of butachlor at \$1.22/kg formulated product (5% granules). ^e Based on a rough rice price of \$0.21/kg.

treatments and weed control methods, including a weed-free and weedy check, were main plot treatments.

Seedlings were transplanted in lines at 20- × 20- cm spacing in a field fertilized with 5 t farmyard manure/ha. Hand and rotary weeding were performed once at 35 d after transplanting (DT), or twice at 21 and 40 DT. Butachlor granules were broadcast 2 DT at 2 kg ai/ha with or without one hand or rotary weeding at 35 DT. Weeding costs were estimated on the basis of current labor charges, cost of herbicide, and time taken to apply it.

A minimum 10 m² from the center of each plot was harvested to determine grain yield. Weed control methods were compared to local farmer practice (one hand weeding) by calculating return above variable cost (RAVC) and marginal benefit-to-cost ratio (MBCR).

Principal weed species were *Cyperus rotundus* and *Fimbristylis miliacea*. Other species found were *Cyperus* spp., *Cynodon dactylon*, *Echinochloa* spp. and *Paspalum distichum*. All weed control treatments gave a significantly higher yield than the weedy check (see table). Response of the varieties to the treatments was broadly similar. The highest yields, comparable to that of the weed-free check, came from the butachlor treatments and were not significantly different from yields with one or two hand or rotary weeding. There was no yield advantage in supplementing butachlor with hand or rotary weeding. A single rotary weeding 35 DT appeared to be more effective than a single hand weeding, and was statistically comparable to 2 rotary weeding.

Compared with farmer practice (one hand weeding), rotary weeding treatments had substantial RAVC, reflecting both reduced costs and increased benefits. But unlike the alternative weed control treatments, which can be applied in randomly planted rice (the common practice in Wangdiphodrang), rotary weeding requires line planting. That may entail increased costs if more planting time is needed.

Of the remaining treatments, a second hand weeding gave some economic advantage over farmer practice, but a single application of butachlor was outstanding economically.

Both butachlor and rotary weeding appear to be promising labor-saving weed control methods in rice under Bhutanese conditions. □

Weeds disseminated with rice seedlings

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In Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, we observed that weed seedlings and weed seeds were disseminated with rice seedlings during transplanting. An average of 51 weed seedlings were counted in each of 450 rice seedling bundles, which contained an average 684 rice seedlings. Farmers did not separate out the weed seedlings before transplanting.

Fourteen species belonging to five families were transplanted with the rice seedlings: the most common were

Echinochloa glabrescens and *Paspalum distichum* (see table). These weeds are highly competitive with rice and difficult to control.

An average 427 weed seeds were found attached to the roots of rice seedlings in each of 300 bundles examined. Twenty weed species, predominantly *Cyperus difformis*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Rotala catholica*, and *Lindernia antipoda*, which were disseminated in this manner, added to the weed seed reserves in the soil. Depending on dormancy and viability, they will be a source of infestation, not only in the crop in which they were disseminated but also in future crops. □

Weeds disseminated with rice seedlings in farmers fields, Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Weed species	Family	Seedlings (no.)	Seeds (no.)
<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Lythraceae	—	10.5
<i>Ammannia octandra</i> L. f.	Lythraceae	—	16.2
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	5.7	104.0
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	0.1	3.3
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	1.1	1.8
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	1.2	—
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	3.1	2.8
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook. f.	Poaceae	10.9	9.3
<i>Echinochloa oryzoides</i> (Ard.) Fritsch.	Poaceae	5.0	—
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	0.1	3.3
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	4.4	86.5
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Poaceae	0.9	—
<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.) Alston	Scrophulariaceae	0.1	65.7
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	Onagraceae	—	2.8
<i>Ludwigia perennis</i> L.	Onagraceae	—	6.7
<i>Melochia concatenata</i> L.	Sterculiaceae	—	0.2
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl	Pontederiaceae	0.3	25.2
<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	13.6	0.8
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Poaceae	—	0.3
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schum. & Thonn.	Euphorbiaceae	—	0.3
<i>Rotala catholica</i> (Cham. & Schlecht.) B. van Leeuwen	Lythraceae	—	67.5
<i>Scirpus supinus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	4.8	18.7
<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> L.	Aizoaceae	—	1.5

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